

ISMA INFORMĀCIJAS
SISTĒMU
MENEDŽMENTA
ANNO 1994 AUGSTSKOLA

ISMA University of Applied Sciences

International scientific conference

**NEW APPROACHES
AND CURRENT LEGAL RESEARCH**

November 3–4, 2022

IZDEVNIECĪBA
BALTĪJA
PUBLISHING

2022

International scientific conference «New approaches and current legal research»: conference proceedings (November 3–4, 2022. Riga, the Republic of Latvia). Riga, Latvia : “Baltija Publishing”, 2022. 208 pages.

HEAD OF ORGANISING COMMITTEE

Romans Djakons, Dr.sc.ing., Professor, Academician, President of ISMA University of Applied Sciences.

Each author is responsible for content and formation of his/her materials.

The reference is mandatory in case of republishing or citation.

CONTENTS

HISTORY AND THEORY OF LAW AND STATE

The police ombudsman role in the protection of human rights and freedoms in Ukraine under the conditions of military aggression

Datsiuk T. K., Dzevytska L. S., Kravtsova M. O.8

Gender component of modern education

Zaiats N. V.12

To the question of the system of scientific categories in jurisprudence

Mytrofanov I. I.15

General theoretical analysis of the essence of the state

Nazarenko O. A.20

Understanding of the obligation by R. von Jhering in the work
“The Purpose in Law”

Popovych T. P.23

The concept and essence of the educational function of the state

Seredunko A. A.26

Functional characteristics of the Ukrainian statehood
(some theoretical considerations)

Sivak V. M.30

Historical and legal experience of the health care system of Ukraine:
case study of evacuation hospitals and bed capacity

Turchina M. O., Kazak R. A.34

The Right to Justice: The Case of the «Polish Vagabonds» (1795-1802)

Forostiuk O. D.37

CONSTITUTIONAL AND MUNICIPAL LAW

«Municipal man» as the basic concept of local democracy

Baymuratov M. O., Kofman B. Ya.40

Constitutional and legal support for the development of mediation in Ukraine

Derkach V. V.44

Constitutional and legal fundamentals of civil society in Ukraine

Zastavna O. P.47

Enhancing constitutional and legal guarantees of person's
and citizen's political rights and freedoms as the key to development
of the rule of law and civil society in Ukraine
Rehushevskiy E. Ye...... 51

CIVIL LAW AND CIVIL PROCEDURE. FAMILY LAW

The concept and essence of the principle of voluntariness
in the mediation procedure
Vasylieva-Shalamova Z. V., Karpiak Ya. A...... 56

Departure of a child abroad: current problems
Horban N. S...... 61

Classification of genetic information as an object of civil law regulation
Krushelnyska H. L...... 65

Something about extrajudicial dispute resolution in the civil procedure
of Ukraine and England
Minchenko R. M., Minchenko D. A...... 69

The scope of freedom of will of a juvenile
Savchenko V. O...... 74

Local corporate lawmaking as a tool for filling gaps in the corporate
legislation of Ukraine
Sulyma A. P...... 76

ECONOMIC LAW AND ECONOMIC PROCEDURE

Certain aspects of the preemptive right implementation to purchase
a share in an LLC
Lukomska O. V...... 81

Assessment of the possibilities of legal support for the establishment
of the ideology of social justice in society using the conclusions of scientific
schools of the economic and legal profile and post-war factors
Mishchenko V. S...... 85

LABOR LAW AND SOCIAL WELFARE LAW

Unemployment in Ukraine as one of the global consequences
of full-scale the Russian aggression
Burka A. V., Bodnaruk M. I...... 89

The role of conciliation bodies in resolving collective labor disputes Kuznetsova M. Yu., Tkachenko V. V.	93
Peculiarities of the implementation of the right to work in the conditions of martial law in Ukraine Mozechuk L. V.	97
AGRARIAN AND ENVIRONMENTAL LAW. LAND LAW	
The problem of land protection in Ukraine Danylyuk S. M.	102
Legal problems of environmental safety (in the context of armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine): international and national legal aspects Kovtun O. M.	105
ADMINISTRATIVE LAW AND PROCEDURE.	
FINANCE LAW. INFORMATION LAW	
Modern theory of information law: questions of methodology Aristova I. V.	109
Subjects of administrative regulation of the placement of orphans and children deprived of parental care according to the legislation of Ukraine Dychko N. V.	112
Directions of the development of administrative and legal security for the introduction of e-education in Ukraine Kluban M. V.	116
Theoretical and praxeological aspects of implementation the principle of collegiality in the activities of local councils (on example of the Ukraine) Lisnichenko A. S.	120
Ways of judicial protection of subjective public rights Marchenko O. O.	124
To the issue of tools for protecting the subjective rights of participants in administrative relations, such as compensation for damage caused by illegal actions (inaction) of public administration subjects Riabchenko Ya. S.	128

Influence of e-commerce on peculiarities of legal regulation of customs formalities for goods in international postal and express shipments in Ukraine Slychko S. V.	132
Special features of the procedure of exemption from financial liability for non-fulfillment of tax duties during the martial law in Ukraine Smakohrai M. K.	136
To the issue of the legal nature of tax conflicts Chaika V. V.	141
French experience of administrative and legal regulation in the field of natural gas production and gas supply policy Yumoranov D. I.	144
CRIMINAL LAW AND CRIMINOLOGY.	
CRIMINAL AND PENAL LAW	
On issues of development of criminal responsibility for collaboration activity (on the example of the draft bill No. 7279 dated from April 12 th , 2022) Akimov M. O.	148
Collaborative activity: criminal characteristic of the objective side of the crime Vasylenko Y. V.	152
Psychodynamic structure of the subject's personality criminal offence Veresha R. V.	156
The imposition of a milder punishment than provided by law under the legislation of Ukraine and the Republic of Latvia Konovalchik Ye. O.	160
Criminal legal protection of civil aviation against acts of illegal interference: international experience Moshniaha L. V., Yermolenko-Kniazieva L. S., Kniazieva K.	164
Features of the qualification of theft committed under the conditions of the state of martial Nikolaienko T. B., Bilyk A. A.	168
On the issue of systematization of the characteristics of victims of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction Pyvovarov V. V., Sirets O. O.	171

CRIMINAL PROCEDURE AND CRIMINALISTICS

General conditions of trial as determinants of court tactics
in criminal proceedings

Myroshnychenko Yu. M.175

Computer intelligent technologies in anti-corruption monitoring
of legislative and law enforcement processes

Shyrovkov V. A., Nadutenko M. V., Yuschenko S. S.179

**EUROPEAN UNION LAW. INTERNATIONAL LAW
AND COMPARATIVE LAW**

The role of civil society in combating corruption in the European Union
(Integrity Pacts)

Bocharova N. V., Shkabaro V. M., Paleeva Y. S......184

The necessity of global reform of Security Council – is a challenge
of our time

Krasnikova O. V.188

Legal personality of international organizations
(on the example of the International Maritime Organization)

Prots O. Ye.192

The Black Sea grain initiative: the importance of the WTO engagement
to ensure human rights in the context of food security

Rashevskaya K. Ye.196

«Grain corridor» in Ukraine: principles of operation and implementation
of the project

Surilova A. O.199

Regulation of online gambling platforms in EU legislation

Shcherbak H. R.204

2. Кримінальний кодекс України: Закон України від 05.04.2001 № 2341– III. URL: <https://cutt.ly/2BgHvvv> (дата звернення: 05.10.2022).

3. Актуальні проблеми кримінально-правової кваліфікації: нав. посіб./ За заг. ред. В.В. Топчія, наук. ред. В.І. Антипова. Вінниця: ТОВ «Нілан-ЛТД», 2017. 896 с.

4. Про внесення змін до Кримінального кодексу України щодо посилення відповідальності за мародерство: Пояснювальна записка. URL: <https://cutt.ly/TBvaPvw> (дата звернення: 05.10.2022).

DOI <https://doi.org/10.30525/978-9934-26-263-0-43>

**ON THE ISSUE OF SYSTEMATIZATION OF THE
CHARACTERISTICS OF VICTIMS OF CRIMINAL OFFENSES
COMMITTED IN THE FIELD OF HOUSING CONSTRUCTION**

**ДО ПИТАННЯ СИСТЕМАТИЗАЦІЇ ОЗНАК ЖЕРТВ
КРИМІНАЛЬНИХ ПРАВОПОРУШЕНЬ, ВЧИНЮВАНИХ
У СФЕРІ ЖИТЛОВОГО БУДІВНИЦТВА**

Ryvovarov V. V.

*Doctor of Philosophy, Docent,
Academician Stashis Scientific
Research Institute
for the Study of Crime Problems
Kharkiv, Ukraine*

Пивоваров В. В.

*кандидат юридичних наук, доцент,
Науково-дослідний інститут
вивчення проблем злочинності
імені академіка В. В. Сташиса
м. Харків, Україна*

Sirets O. O.

*Postgraduate Student
Academician Stashis Scientific
Research Institute
for the Study of Crime Problems
Kharkiv, Ukraine*

Сірець О. О.

*аспірант
Науково-дослідний інститут
вивчення проблем злочинності
імені академіка В. В. Сташиса
м. Харків, Україна*

We consider it possible to put forward the hypothesis that the key empirical basis for studying the problems of crime in the field of housing construction is Art. 190, 191, 197-1, 364-1 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. In the context of this hypothesis, we can state that the nature of the victim of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction is complex,

since in fact a number of interrelated illegal acts are committed in this field, often in combination. Among the primary tasks of such research is the task of systematizing the characteristics of victims of such criminal offenses, primarily with the aim of deriving a probable generalized portrait of victims of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction.

Of course, depending on the subject composition, the number of victims of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction can include not only individuals, but also legal entities, territorial communities and the state. At the same time, territorial communities and the state are often only able to act as indirect victims (except for territorial communities, which can also become direct victims in exceptional cases – for example, as owners or tenants of a certain land plot). Legal entities as victims also have their own characteristics, since, being a corporate entity, they are not endowed with specific psychological and social features inherent in individual natural persons, which are of exclusive interest to the sciences of criminology and victimology. Therefore, an individual as the victim occupies the main place in our study.

By analyzing the characteristics of the victims of the above-mentioned criminal offenses, as well as the victim characteristics of an entrepreneur, with the subsequent systematization of such characteristics and their generalization, a natural person as a victim of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction should be characterized as follows:

1. In terms of gender, based on the analyzed previous studies, we can note that, probably, the overwhelming majority of this category of victims are men. At the same time, we emphasize the fundamental aspect that the modern social and family role of women has not only changed, but also significantly increased to the level of equating the importance of men and women.

2. Through the generalization of information from previous studies, it was established that the average age of the victims is 28-50 years.

3. Despite the presence in a number of other studies of references to the significance of the social origin or level of education of the victim of the considered types of criminal offenses, we assume that they do not play a fundamental role in forming the portrait of the victim of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction. The reason for this is a number of specific features of modern society (including the domestic one), in particular: firstly, the presence of a high level of education of a certain person, on the one hand, does not necessarily correspond to the level of intellectual development of such a person, on the other hand, and vice versa; secondly, there are precedents when individuals without a high level of education achieved significant achievements.

4. The income level of potential victims of this category is average and higher.

5. According to previous studies, the victims in the absolute majority of cases are local residents and citizens of Ukraine. We must disagree with such a thesis and assume its irrelevance in connection with the high mobility of modern society, both domestically and internationally. Thus, we believe that the issues of place of residence and citizenship do not play a decisive role in depicting the portrait of a victim of criminal offenses committed in the field of housing construction.

6. For the most part, a positive portrait of the victim in question is inherent, characterized in the vast majority of cases by the absence of a criminal past of such a person, as well as the absence of immoral guidelines in the course of life.

7. Such a person is characterized by a number of signs, including activity, publicity, even demonstrativeness, optimism, self-confidence, sufficient success.

8. As a general rule, a potential victim of this category meets high social standards, in particular, is characterized by high social adaptability.

9. The considered potential victim is capable of forming a mental conclusion, making strategic decisions. At the same time, although to a much lesser extent, self-confidence, credulity, carelessness, even uncriticalness when perceiving information are characteristic of her.

10. One of the most distinctive characteristics of a victim of a criminal offense committed in the field of housing construction is his propensity to risk.

In addition, for this category of victims, there are also other signs, which, however, we convincingly consider optional, since they are not universally obligatory and present in all cases, but rather are considered to be able to supplement the general portrait of the victim of this category for its better understanding. Such signs are:

1. Demonstrative superiority in relation to others.

2. Boasting of the existence of corrupt connections in the authorities, presumably accompanied by disregard for the requirements of the law.

3. In many cases, victims of this category of criminal offenses are persons who do not have their own home at the time of investment.

4. In the vast majority of cases, victims learn about the possibility of investing in real estate from advertisements placed on various platforms, less often – the source of information is other people [1, p. 65-66; 2, p. 175-177; 3, p. 119-120; 4, p. 93; 5, p. 145; 6, p. 56; 7, p. 117-121].

In conclusion, it should be noted that modern social relations are developing and changing, and in connection with this, it is impossible for this

study to fully cover the comprehensive range of specific characteristics inherent in the considered category of victims. Therefore, there is an urgent need to continue the criminological research of this problem in further scientific developments.

Literature:

1. Кузьменко С. С. Розслідування шахрайства, пов'язаного з інвестуванням коштів у будівництво об'єктів нерухомості: дис. канд. юрид. наук: 12.00.09 / С. С. Кузьменко. Київ, 2019. 227 с.
2. Чернишов Г. М. Фінансове шахрайство в інвестиційно-будівельній сфері: кримінологічне дослідження: дис. канд. юрид. наук: 12.00.08 / Г. М. Чернишов. Одеса, 2016. 255 с.
3. Лысодед А. В. Криминологические проблемы мошенничества: дис. канд. юрид. наук: 12.00.08 / А. В. Лысодед. Харьков, 1999. 215 с.
4. Бруссо К. М. Розслідування корупційних кримінальних правопорушень, які вчиняються в сфері житлового будівництва: дис. канд. юрид. наук: 12.00.09 / К. М. Бруссо. Маріуполь, 2021. 268 с.
5. Татарин Н. М. Криміналістична характеристика самовільного зайняття земельної ділянки та самовільного будівництва. Юридичний науковий електронний журнал. 2014. № 1. С. 142-146.
6. Методика розслідування окремих видів злочинів: навч. посібник / О. І. Герасимів, О. М. Дуфенюк, О. В. Захарова та ін.; за заг. ред. Є. В. Пряхіна, 2-ге вид., перероб. та допов. Львів: ЛьвДУВС, 2019. 312 с.
7. Віктимологія: : навч. посібник / В. В. Голіна, Б. М. Головкін, М. Ю. Валуйська та ін.; за ред. В. В. Голіни і Б. М. Головкіна. Харків.: Право, 2017. 308 с.

International scientific conference «New approaches and current legal research»

November 3–4, 2022

Izdevniecība «Baltija Publishing»
Valdeķu iela 62 – 156, Rīga, LV-1058
E-mail: office@baltijapublishing.lv

Iespiests tipogrāfijā SIA «Izdevniecība «Baltija Publishing»
Parakstīts iespiešanai: 2022. 8. novembris
Tirāža 100 eks.